

AI-INDUCED PEDAGOGY AND THE ENHANCEMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' LEARNING OUTCOMES IN COORDINATE GEOMETRY IN BAYELSA STATE

BY

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of AI-induced Pedagogy on the enhancement of secondary school students' learning outcomes in coordinate geometry in Bayelsa State. A quasi-experimental, pre-test, post-test non-equivalent control group design was adopted. The population comprised all senior secondary school students offering Mathematics in the state, with a sample of 179 SS II students drawn from two purposively selected schools that had functional ICT facilities. Intact classes were randomly assigned to the experimental group, which was taught using AI-induced Pedagogy, and the control group, which was taught using the conventional lecture method. The Coordinate Geometry Achievement Test (CGAT) was developed by the researcher and subjected to expert validation, while reliability was established using Kuder–Richardson 20 (KR-20), yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.82. Pre-test and post-test scores were collected to measure students' learning outcomes. Two research questions and two corresponding hypotheses guided the study. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that students taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy achieved significantly higher gains than those taught using the conventional method, and that there was no significant difference in achievement between male and female students taught with AI-induced Pedagogy. The study recommends the integration of AI-induced instructional strategies into secondary school mathematics teaching to improve students' learning outcomes in coordinate geometry.

Keywords: AI-induced Pedagogy, Achievement, Coordinate Geometry, Secondary School Students

Introduction

Mathematics plays a pivotal role in the scientific, technological, and economic development of any nation. It serves as the foundation for various disciplines, including engineering, medicine, and information technology. Charles-Owaba (2019) submitted that proficiency in mathematics provides individuals with broader career options and enhances problem-solving capabilities. The National Policy on Education (NPE, 2014) underscores the importance of mathematics by making it a compulsory subject at the primary and secondary school levels, emphasizing the need for effective teaching strategies to

improve students' comprehension and performance.

Despite its significance, students' performance in mathematics, particularly in coordinate geometry, has remained persistently low. The West African Examinations Council (WAEC) Chief Examiner's Report (2020) highlighted that students exhibit considerable weaknesses in understanding and applying coordinate geometry concepts, leading to poor achievement in standardized examinations. Research by Uwadiace (2018) indicated that less than 42% of students achieve a credit pass in mathematics, with coordinate geometry identified as one of the most challenging

topics. Several factors contribute to this trend, including students' anxiety towards mathematics, abstract nature of the subject, and ineffective teaching methodologies (Abakpa & Iji, 2021).

Traditional teaching methods, which rely heavily on rote memorization and passive learning, have been identified as major contributors to students' poor achievement in mathematics (Olunoye, 2020). Studies have shown that conventional instructional approaches fail to actively engage students, making it difficult for them to grasp abstract mathematical concepts (Basturk & Yavuz, 2020). Consequently, there has been an increasing call for the integration of innovative pedagogical strategies that can enhance students' learning experiences and outcomes. Among such emerging strategies is the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education.

AI-induced Pedagogy leverages machine learning algorithms, adaptive learning systems, and intelligent tutoring to provide personalized instruction tailored to students' individual learning needs. Charles-Owaba (2025) reported that AI-powered educational tools analyze students' learning patterns and provide customized learning experiences, enabling them to better understand complex mathematical concepts. AI-based instructional platforms, such as Carnegie Learning's MATHia, have demonstrated significant improvements in students' mathematical performance by offering real-time feedback and adaptive learning pathways. The integration of AI in mathematics instruction, therefore, holds the potential to bridge learning gaps and improve students' achievement in coordinate geometry.

Moreover, AI-induced Pedagogy has the advantage of fostering interactive and engaging learning environments. Research by Charles-Owaba (2024) revealed that AI-based learning tools incorporating gamification elements, such as rewards and progress

tracking, significantly enhance students' motivation and interest in mathematics. Increased engagement through interactive learning environments not only improves comprehension but also alleviates math anxiety, which has been identified as a major barrier to students' success in the subject (Ebele & Sam, 2015). The use of AI in education also facilitates immediate feedback and continuous assessment, allowing students to identify and rectify errors promptly, thereby reinforcing their learning process.

Gender disparities in mathematics achievement have also been a subject of debate among scholars. Some studies suggest that male students tend to outperform their female counterparts in geometry and mensuration, while others argue that the difference is negligible (Abiam & Odok, 2016). Amelink (2019) found that instructional strategies significantly influence gender-based achievement differences in mathematics. This suggests that AI-induced Pedagogy, with its individualized and adaptive nature, could provide an equitable learning experience for both male and female students, thereby reducing gender-related disparities in achievement.

Despite the growing body of research on AI in education, empirical evidence on its effectiveness in teaching coordinate geometry, particularly in Nigerian secondary schools, remains scarce. Most existing studies have focused on broader applications of AI in mathematics without addressing its specific impact on students' achievement in coordinate geometry (Charles-Owaba, 2025). Given the critical role of coordinate geometry in advanced mathematical applications and students' persistent struggles with the topic, it is imperative to explore innovative teaching methods that can improve their learning outcomes. This study, therefore, investigated the effect of AI-Induced Pedagogy on students' achievement in coordinate geometry in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Purpose of the Study

The study examined the effect of AI-induced Pedagogy on the enhancement of secondary school students' learning outcome in coordinate geometry in secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study achieved the following:

- i. Determine the difference in mean achievement scores of students taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy and those taught using conventional methods.
- ii. Determine the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

- i. What is the difference in mean achievement scores between students taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy and those taught using conventional methods?
- ii. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy?

Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated and tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy and those taught using conventional methods.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy.

Methodology

The study employed a pre-test, post-test, non-equivalent control group quasi-experimental design. This design was adopted to enable the investigation of intact classes in a natural classroom environment, as random assignment of students to treatment conditions during normal school hours was impractical and could create artificial learning situations. The design therefore allowed for a realistic comparison of students taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy and those taught using the conventional teaching method, as well as gender-based comparison within the experimental group.

The population of the study comprised all senior secondary school students offering Mathematics in Bayelsa State. A sample of SS II students was used for the study. Two co-educational public secondary schools were purposively selected based on the availability of basic ICT facilities required for the implementation of AI-induced instructional strategies. The SS II class was deliberately chosen because the topic of coordinate geometry is adequately covered at this level and the students were not preparing for any immediate external examinations that could interfere with active participation in the study. In each of the selected schools, several SS II streams were available. From these, intact classes were selected using simple random sampling technique. The selected classes were randomly assigned to either the experimental group or the control group through balloting.

The experimental group was taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy, while the control group was taught the same content using the conventional lecture method. All the SS II students in the selected classes constituted the sample for the study.

The instrument for data collection was the Coordinate Geometry Achievement Test (CGAT) developed by the researcher. The CGAT consisted of two parts: Part I elicited personal information of the respondents such

as gender and school, while Part II comprised 30 multiple-choice items drawn from coordinate geometry topics including distance between two points, midpoint of a line segment, gradient of a straight line, equation of straight lines, and simple applications of coordinate geometry. The test items were structured in line with the SS II Mathematics curriculum as prescribed by the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC). Each item had four options (A, B, C, and D), with one correct answer. Each correctly answered item attracted one mark, making a total of 30 marks obtainable.

The CGAT was subjected to face and content validation by two Mathematics Education experts and one Measurement and Evaluation expert to ensure adequacy of content coverage, clarity of items, and appropriateness of difficulty level. The reliability of the CGAT was established using the Kuder–Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20), and a reliability coefficient of 0.82 was obtained, which was considered adequate for the study.

The experiment was carried out in three stages: pre-test, treatment, and post-test. During the pre-test stage, the CGAT was administered to both the experimental and control groups to determine their initial equivalence. During the treatment stage, the experimental group was

taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy, which involved the use of AI-supported instructional tools such as adaptive learning platforms, interactive problem-solving applications, and intelligent feedback systems. The control group received instruction using the conventional lecture method. The treatment lasted for four weeks, with equal instructional time allotted to both groups. At the end of the treatment, the CGAT was re-administered to both groups as a post-test.

The data collected were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (SD) were used to answer the research questions, while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The ANCOVA was employed to determine the effect of AI-induced Pedagogy on students’ learning outcome while statistically controlling for initial differences in achievement. The pre-test scores served as the covariate in the analysis.

Research Question 1: What is the difference in mean achievement scores between students taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy and those taught using conventional methods?

Table 1: Mean Achievement Scores, Standard Deviations and Mean Gain of Students Taught Using AIP and Lecture Method

Groups	N	Pre-CGAT		Post-CGAT		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Experimental	86	5.91	2.90	26.63	6.57	20.72
Control	93	7.52	3.63	17.90	3.96	10.33

Source: Fieldwork (2025)

The table above shows that the experimental group, which consisted of students taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy, obtained a mean achievement

score of 5.91 with a standard deviation of 2.90 in the Pre-CGAT and a mean achievement score of 26.63 with a standard deviation of 6.57 in the Post-CGAT. This indicates a substantial improvement in the achievement

level of students exposed to AI-induced instructional strategies.

It was also revealed that the control group, representing students taught coordinate geometry using the conventional lecture method, recorded a mean achievement score of 7.52 with a standard deviation of 3.63 in the Pre-CGAT and a mean achievement score of 17.90 with a standard deviation of 3.96 in the Post-CGAT. Although there was an improvement in performance after instruction, the increase was comparatively lower than that of the experimental group.

Furthermore, the standard deviations for both groups increased from the pre-test to the post-test, indicating a wider spread of scores as students' mean achievement improved. However, the spread of scores was higher among students taught using AI-induced

Pedagogy than among those taught with the lecture method, suggesting greater variability in learning gains within the experimental group.

The mean gain analysis further shows that the experimental group recorded a mean gain of 20.72, while the control group recorded a mean gain of 10.33. This clearly implies that students taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy achieved a higher improvement in learning outcomes compared to their counterparts taught using the conventional lecture method.

Research Question 2: What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy?

Table 2: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Students Taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy

Sex	N	Pre CGAT		Post-CGAT		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Male	50	13.89	1.04	21.17	6.76	7.28
Female	36	13.13	1.10	21.93	6.32	8.80

The table above shows that male students taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy recorded a mean achievement score of 13.89 with a standard deviation of 1.04 in the Pre-CGAT and a mean achievement score of 21.17 with a standard deviation of 6.76 in the Post-CGAT. This result indicates an improvement in the achievement of male students after exposure to AI-induced instructional strategies.

Similarly, female students taught using AI-induced Pedagogy obtained a mean achievement score of 13.13 with a standard deviation of 1.10 in the Pre-CGAT and a mean achievement score of 21.93 with a standard deviation of 6.32 in the Post-CGAT. This also shows a notable improvement in the achievement level of female students following instruction with AI-induced Pedagogy.

The standard deviations for both male and female students increased from the pre-test to the post-test, indicating a wider spread of scores as students' achievement levels improved. However, the variability in scores was slightly higher among male students than female students in the post-test. Furthermore, the mean gain scores reveal that male students recorded a mean gain of 7.28, while female students recorded a mean gain of 8.80. This suggests that although both male and female students benefited from AI-induced Pedagogy, female students achieved a slightly higher improvement in learning outcomes than their male counterparts when taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy.

Ho: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced

Pedagogy and those taught using conventional methods.

Table 3: Summary of Analysis of Covariance on Experimental and Control Group over achievement

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	3601.688 ^a	4	900.422	31.776	.000	.422
Intercept	14914.573	1	14914.573	526.343	.000	.752
PREGAT	74.292	1	74.292	2.622	.107	.015
METHOD	3501.507	1	3501.507	123.570	.000	.415
GENDER	99.938	1	99.938	3.527	.062	.020
METHOD * GENDER	.497	1	.497	.018	.895	.000
Error	4930.502	174	28.336			
Total	95962.000	179				
Corrected Total	8532.190	178				

The summary of data analysis presented in Table 3 shows that the main effect of the teaching method on students’ achievement in coordinate geometry has an F-calculated value of 123.570 with a p-value of .000, which is less than the critical p-value of 0.05. This result is based on 1 degree of freedom for the numerator and 174 degrees of freedom for the denominator.

Consequently, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy and those taught using the conventional lecture method. The result further indicates that the teaching method significantly influenced students’ learning outcomes in coordinate geometry in favour of AI-induced Pedagogy.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy.

The summary of data analysis presented in Table 3 shows that the main effect of gender on students’ achievement in coordinate geometry taught using AI-induced Pedagogy has an F-calculated value of 3.527 with a p-

value of .062, which is greater than the critical p-value of 0.05. This result is based on 1 degree of freedom for the numerator and 174 degrees of freedom for the denominator.

Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{02}) is not rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught coordinate geometry using AI-induced Pedagogy. The result indicates that AI-induced Pedagogy is gender-friendly, as it enhances students’ learning outcomes in coordinate geometry without favouring either male or female students.

Discussion of Findings

The findings on method and students’ achievement in coordinate geometry revealed that students taught using AI-induced Pedagogy performed better than those taught using the conventional lecture method. Evidence from the study showed that students in the experimental group recorded a mean gain of 20.72, whereas their counterparts in the control group recorded a mean gain of 10.33, indicating a clear and substantial difference in favour of students exposed to AI-induced instructional strategies. This

suggests that AI-induced Pedagogy was more effective in enhancing students' learning outcomes in coordinate geometry than the traditional lecture method.

The test of Hypothesis 1 further confirmed this observed difference. The ANCOVA result showed a statistically significant effect of teaching method on students' achievement, with an F-value of 123.570 and a p-value of .000, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implies that the difference in mean achievement scores between students taught with AI-induced Pedagogy and those taught with the conventional method did not occur by chance, but rather resulted from the instructional approach adopted. Therefore, AI-induced Pedagogy had a positive and significant effect on students' achievement in coordinate geometry.

This finding is consistent with earlier studies such as those of Gamage and Charles-Ogan (2019), Etsu and Manko (2019), Dimakos (2020), and Yilmaz et al. (2022), who reported that students taught using technology-driven and AI-supported instructional strategies performed significantly better than those taught using traditional teaching methods. These studies emphasized that AI-based and interactive learning environments support visualization, immediate feedback, and personalized learning pathways, which help students grasp abstract concepts in mathematics more effectively. Similarly, Arbenand and Nurbiha (2015) noted that technology-enhanced instruction promotes active learner engagement and conceptual understanding, thereby improving academic achievement.

The findings on gender and students' achievement in coordinate geometry when taught using AI-induced Pedagogy revealed that both male and female students benefited substantially from the instructional approach. Although female students recorded a slightly

higher mean gain (8.80) compared to their male counterparts (7.28), the difference in achievement between the two groups was marginal. This indicates that AI-induced Pedagogy enhanced the learning outcomes of both genders in a relatively balanced manner. The test of Hypothesis 2 further supported this observation. The ANCOVA result showed that gender had no statistically significant effect on students' achievement in coordinate geometry taught using AI-induced Pedagogy, as indicated by an F-value of 3.527 and a p-value of .062, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Consequently, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that the observed difference in mean achievement scores between male and female students was not significant and could be attributed to chance rather than gender influence.

This finding is in agreement with the results of previous studies such as those of Etsu and Manko (2019), Dimakos (2020), and Yilmaz et al. (2022), who reported that technology-based and AI-supported instructional strategies tend to minimize gender disparities in mathematics achievement. These studies noted that adaptive feedback, interactive visualization, and learner-centered features of AI-enhanced instruction create inclusive learning environments that support both male and female learners equally. Similarly, Gamage and Charles-Ogan (2019) observed that digital instructional strategies promote equity in learning by allowing students to learn at their own pace, thereby reducing gender-related performance gaps.

In essence, the findings of this study suggest that AI-induced Pedagogy is gender-neutral and inclusive, as it significantly improves students' achievement in coordinate geometry without favouring either male or female students. This underscores the potential of AI-driven instructional approaches to promote

equity and inclusiveness in mathematics education.

Conclusion

The study concluded that AI-induced Pedagogy is an effective and innovative instructional approach for enhancing secondary school students' learning outcomes in coordinate geometry. The findings demonstrated that students taught using AI-induced Pedagogy achieved significantly higher academic gains than those taught with the conventional lecture method, indicating the superiority of AI-supported instruction in improving understanding and performance in coordinate geometry. Furthermore, the study revealed that the effectiveness of AI-induced Pedagogy was not influenced by gender, as both male and female students benefited equally from the approach. Consequently, AI-induced Pedagogy can be considered a gender-inclusive teaching strategy capable of improving students' achievement in mathematics, and its integration into secondary school mathematics instruction could contribute significantly to improved learning outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that:

1. Mathematics teachers should be encouraged and trained to adopt AI-induced Pedagogy in the teaching of coordinate geometry and other mathematical concepts to enhance students' learning outcomes.
2. Educational stakeholders and school administrators should provide adequate ICT infrastructure and AI-supportive learning resources in secondary schools to facilitate effective implementation of AI-induced instructional strategies.

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